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NanoDefine

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1 Objective

This SOP describes an off-line method for automated image analysis of particulate materials imaged by electron microscopy, which has been developed in the NanoDefine project, referred to as the 'NanoDefine ParticleSizer'. The method allows determining automatically the distributions of the characteristic size and shape properties (section 7) of primary particles in aggregates and agglomerates, or present as single particles, from EM images. This application is specifically designed in the scope of implementing the EC-definition of a nanomaterial. The median value of the number-based distribution of the minimal external dimension of the primary particles is assessed.

2 Application domain

This SOP describes an off-line method for automated image analysis of particulate materials, and requires that the material has been representatively brought on an EM grid e.g. by following the SOP "SOP/NANoREG/D2.10/TEMSpePrep" entitled "Preparation of EM-grids containing a representative sample of a dispersed NM". In addition, the SOP requires that representative images of the material have been recorded by an electron microscopy based imaging technique such as TEM, SEM or STEM, e.g. following the SOP "SOP/NANoREG/D2.10/TEMIma" entitled "Transmission electron microscopic imaging of nanomaterials". The ParticleSizer can also be applied on representative EM micrographs obtained in an alternative way.

The SOP can be used to characterize particulate materials (single particles and aggregated/agglomerated particles) and measure the size and shape properties of the electron microscopic projections of the primary particle of the material.

In the context of implementing the EC definition of a nanomaterial, it produces a number based distribution of the minimal external dimension of the primary particles, assessed as the minimal Feret diameter or short axis length of fitted ellipse. The median value of these parameters allows classifying a material as a nanomaterial according to the EC definition.

The other measured size and shape parameters (Section 7) allow a detailed characterization of the materials required for e.g. risk analysis, batch and process control.

The SOP is tested on a series of certified reference materials (CRMs), such as ERM-FD304 and ERM-FD100 and representative test materials (RTMs), such as NM100, NM103 and NM212, and other materials such as Au Nanoparticles and Nanorods.

3 Principle of the method

The SOP foresees in a general procedure to find suitable configurations of the ParticleSizer for different types of materials based on the amount of overlap between primary particles (type of overlap) and the shape of the primary particles (type of particle) (Table 1). Once a suitable configuration is selected, the images are automatically analysed.

During an automatic analysis, the software automatically detects analyses particles on an image. The gray value is the criterion for the recognition of a particle. Therefore, in order to have successful particle detection, the particles must clearly stand out from the background. All detected particles can be automatically measured. A wide array of measured parameters can be chosen (Section 7).

An overview of the processing pipeline implemented in the ParticleSizer is presented in annex (Section 9).

A) Type of particle	Name	Description
	Ellipsoidal	The outline of the particles can roughly be approximated by an ellipse in 2D images
	Irregular	The outline of the particles is irregular and cannot be approximated by an ellipse in 2D images

B) Type of overlap	Name	Description
	None	No overlap of the particles.
	Touching	These particles touch and do not overlap.
	Slightly overlapping	The particles show a low degree of overlap.
	High or complete overlapping	These particles have a high degree of overlapp.

Table 1: ParticleSizer classification of materials based on A) the shape of the primary particles (Type of particle) and B) amount of overlap between primary particles (Type of overlap).

4 Definitions, abbreviations and norms

CRM	Certified Reference Material
EM	Electron microscopy
NP	Nanoparticle
NRBS	noise reduced and background subtracted
OTB	Object-to-Background
RTM	Representative test material
TEM	Transmission electron microscopy

5 System requirements and installation

The ParticleSizer couples image analysis by Fiji (Schindelin et al. 2012) with data analysis by R (R Development Core Team 2008). Online manuals can be found on the following websites: <http://fiji.sc/> for Fiji and <https://www.r-project.org/> for R

To install the ParticleSizer software, the following procedure has to be followed:

1. Download the latest fiji <http://fiji.sc/#download>
2. Activate the Biomedgroup update site¹
3. Add a new update site² with the name "psizer" and url <http://sites.imagej.net/Ndef-psizer/>. By adding the psizer update site, the ParticleSizer software is updated automatically when Fiji is updated.
4. Do the update. Now the particle sizer should be installed.
5. (Optional): It is recommended to install R to get better plots. When this point is skipped, a stripped-down plot will be shown.
 - 5.1 Download the latest R: <https://cran.uni-muenster.de/>
 - 5.2 Download the Rserver package:
https://rforge.net/bin/windows/contrib/3.0/Rserve_1.8-0.zip
 - 5.3 Download the MASS package:
https://cran.r-project.org/bin/windows/contrib/3.2/MASS_7.3-45.zip
 - 5.4 Start R and select the packages downloaded in 5.2 and 5.3 via "Start Packages -> Install packages from local zip files"
 - 5.5 Open the ParticleSizer settings manager (see 6.2) and set the R installation path. The path should something like: "C://Program Files/R/R-3.1.1/"

1 A manual how to follow a update site could be find here: http://fiji.sc/How_to_follow_a_3rd_party_update_site

2 A manual how to add a new update site could be find here: http://fiji.sc/How_to_follow_a_3rd_party_update_site#Add_update_sites

6 Procedure to analyze sample images

6.1 Start Fiji

To start Fiji, simply open your Fiji folder and click on ImageJ.exe

To open the ParticleSizer, the following procedure has to be followed:

1. Open Fiji
2. Go to plugins
3. Select nanodefine
4. Select particlesizer

6.2 Determine a basic suitable configuration

The software allows the user to set up a configuration suitable for a specific “type of particle” and “type of overlap” combination. The default configuration can be observed by activating the Settings Manager: Plugins → NanoDefine → SettingsManager and is illustrated by figure 1. A default configuration is readily provided and can be applied on simple models with ‘none’ or ‘touching’ particles (figure 2).

The default configuration can be split into 5 categories: mode selection, segmentation, Ellipse shape constraints, shape constraints and miscellaneous (Misc). For each option a default value is defined. The user has the option to optimize the settings for the images that will be analyzed. A detailed description of each of these settings is given in Annex (Section 8).

The default values are as follows:

Figure 1: Settings Manager of the ParticleSizer with default configuration.

Mode selection:

- Use watershed for irregular structures: off
- Irregular watershed convexity threshold: 0.7
- Use single particle mode: off
- Use ellipse fitting mode: off

Shape constraints:

- Minimal area: 0 px
- Minimal feret min: 10 px
- Minimal convexity: 0
- Minimal solidity: 0

Misc

- Smoothing factor: 1
- Show binary result: off
- Ask me to select a region: off

Segmentation:

- Circular window radius: 1.5% of the image width
- Rolling ball radius: 15% of the image width
- Min. OTB intensity difference: 16

Ellipse shape constraints

- Minimal long axis length: 5 px
- Minimal short axis length: 5 px
- Maximal aspect ratio: 100

Figure 2: Procedure to determine suitable mode

In a typical image analysis, the default settings in the Settings Manager have to be optimized for a certain “type of particle” and “type of overlap” combination. Figure 2 shows the general procedure to determine a suitable configuration. The first step is to determine the type of overlap based on visual inspection of the particles. A distinction is made between “none”, “touching”, “slightly overlapping” or “high or complete overlapping” particles. The second step is to determine the type of particle based on visual inspection of the particles. A distinction is made between “ellipsoidal” or “irregular” particles. Besides the image quality the combination of overlapping type and particle type determines the configuration.

Depending on the selected “type of particle” and “type of overlap” combination, a suitable algorithm is selected for image analysis. These can be “Default”, “Irregular Watershed”, “Ellipse fitting” or “Single particle mode”.

For “Irregular watershed”, “Ellipse fitting”, “Single particle mode”, the boxes “Use watershed for irregular structures”, “Use ellipse fitting mode” or “Use single particle mode” have to be checked, respectively. The method can be readily applied on “none”, “touching” or “slightly overlapping” particles. For difficult materials, different modes can be combined. For particles with a high degree of overlap, single particle mode can be used on the condition that the single particles have the same physical properties as the primary particles in aggregates/agglomerates. If this is not the case, the large aggregates/agglomerates have to be separated by optimizing the sample preparation.

The following general rules should be ensured:

If the image contains a scale bar, this could interfere the analysis process. Therefore the largest possible region which does not contain the scale bar has to be selected. To do this, please check the option "Ask me to select a region".

The software expects bright particles on a dark background. If this is not the case, please check the option "Use inverted images".

6.3 Image analysis

To apply the ParticleSizer to your sample data, select "Plugins → NanoDefine → ParticleSizer".

A single image can be opened by "File → Open". If a whole image series (stack) should be analysed it can be opened by "File → Import → Image Sequence". The option "Convert to 8-Bit Grayscale" should be checked. If the whole sequence does not fit in the memory, check "Use virtual stack" in the sequence options.

6.4 Optional: Optimize the analysis

Certain artefacts might occur during the image analysis, which can have an influence on the results. The following strategies give advice how to proceed in those cases.

6.4.1 Some low contrast particles are not detected

Open the configure dialog by "Plugins → NanoDefine → Settings Manager", decrease the "Min. OTB intensity difference" by 2, and apply the ParticleSizer again. Repeat this until all particles are detected. By lowering the OTB difference it could happen that some small parts of the background are detected as particles. Experience shows that these objects are rather small and could be filtered out by increasing "Minimal area" or "Minimal feret min".

6.4.2 Background is detected as particles

IF the artefacts are as large as the smallest particles, then

increase the "Min. OTB intensity difference" by 2, press OK and apply the ParticleSizer again. Repeat this until you get reasonable results.

IF the artefacts are smaller than the smallest particles, then

increase the "Minimal feret min" diameter until they are removed. The minimal feret diameter can be estimated by measuring the smallest dimension of the largest artefact with the line tool . If the images are scaled, than press "ALT" while using the line tool to get it in pixels.

6.4.3 Use "record process" to analyse the segmentation processing

If you check the option "record process" every single interim image (segmentation step) is recorded. In the top left of the corner is written which step was recorded. This option can be used to determine which settings have to be optimized. Please note that the "record process" option only works for a single image, not for a complete stack.

7 Output of results

There are several geometrical features which are calculated and saved into a results table by the ParticleSizer software. The table could be exported by the user. The geometrical features are defined as follows:

- **Area (A):** The area enclosed by the outer contour of the particle.
- **Area convex hull (C):** The area enclosed by the convex hull of the outer contour of the particle.
- **Perimeter (P):** The perimeter of the outer contour of the particle.
- **Perimeter convex hull (H):** The perimeter of the convex hull of the particle.
- **Maximum Feret diameter:** The maximum distance between the two parallel tangents touching the particle outline in all directions.
- **Minimum Feret diameter:** the minimum distance between the two parallel tangents touching the particle outline in all directions.
- **Long side minimum bounding rectangle (L):** The larger side of the minimum bounding rectangle.

- **Short side minimum bounding rectangle (S):** The smaller side of the minimum bounding rectangle.
- **Aspect ratio:** Defined as L/S .
- **Area / Perimeter ratio:** Defined as A/P .
- **Circularity:** Defined as P^2/A .
- **Elongation:** Defined as $1 - S/L$.
- **Convexity:** Defined as H/P .
- **Solidity:** Defined as A/C .
- **Number of holes:** The number of holes inside a particle.
- **Thinness ratio:** Inversely proportional to the circularity and normed. It is defined as $4\pi A/P^2$.
- **Contour temperature:** It has a strong relationship to the fractal dimension, defined as $(\log_2(\frac{2P}{P_H}))^2$.
- **Fractal dimension:** Estimated fractal dimension by the box count algorithm. The default box-sizes are "2,3,4,6,8,12,16,32,64".
- **Maximum inscribed circle diameter:** Computes the largest inner circle of a particle.

The default plot is the minimum Feret diameter (Figure 3). However, if the ellipse fitting mode is used, the short axis length is reported which is equivalent to the minimum feret diameter. Directly below the plot, all used settings are documented for easily reproduction. Below the title the median value is outputted. By right clicking on the histogram and selecting "Modify Plot", the X-axis and Y-axis labels and the number of bins can be altered. In addition, a function selected in the Fit Distribution field can be fitted through the histogram. Other geometric features could be plotted by selecting in Results table "Results → Distribution". Finally the plot could be exported by "File → Save as". Furthermore the segmented particles are visualized by an overlay (red lines) on top on the input image (Figure 4)

Path: L45AB-1		
Number of particles: 923	Minimal Area: 0	Smoothing factor: 10
Circular window size: 60	Minimal Feret Min.: 10	Irregular Watershed (IWS): false
Rolling ball radius: 614.4	Minimal Convexity: 0	IWS Convexity Threshold: 0.85
Averaged minimal object intensity: 10	Minimal Solidity: 0	Single particle mode: false

Figure 3: Size distribution of the minimal Feret diameter for a polystyrene sample

Figure 4: Segmented particles shown as overlay (red circles)

8 Appendix A: Description of adjustable settings in the Settings Manager

Mode selection:

- Use watershed for irregular structures: If selected, the mode for irregular structures is used. See section 9.3 for details.
- Irregular watershed convexity threshold: A threshold which determines, the amount of splitting up agglomerates. If the convexity of a particle is larger than this threshold, the splitting is stopped for this object. If the convexity is smaller than this threshold, the Software tries to split the particle again.
- Use single particle mode: If selected, the single particle mode is used. See section 9.5 for details.
- Use ellipse fitting mode: If selected, the ellipse fitting mode is used. See section 9.4 for details.

Segmentation:

- Circular window radius: This is a parameter of the local thresholding technique. The ParticleSizer does not use a global threshold to binarize the image. Instead it uses a local threshold which is estimated for a specific circular region with the configured radius.
- Rolling ball radius: The background is removed by rolling a ball with this radius over the surface (intensity interpreted as height) of the image. It should be at least as large as the largest object in image which does not belong to the background.
- Min. OTB intensity difference: Objects which have an object-to-background (OTB) intensity difference in the noise-reduced and background subtracted image (see section 9.2) lower than this threshold are considered as artefacts and are removed.

Shape constraints:

- Minimal area: Minimum area in pixels. Particles smaller than this threshold are removed.
- Minimal feret min: Minimal feret diameter in pixels. Particles smaller than this threshold are removed.
- Minimal convexity: The convexity is defined as the ratio of the perimeter of the convex hull of the particle and the perimeter of the particle. It lies between 0 and 1. The convexity increases with larger values. Particles smaller than this threshold are removed.
- Minimal solidity: Defined as the ratio of the particle area and the area of the convex hull of the particle. It lies between 0 and 1. The solidity increases with larger values. Particles smaller than this threshold are removed.

Ellipse shape constraints

- Minimal long axis length: The length in pixels of the major direction of the fitted ellipse. Ellipses smaller than this threshold are removed.
- Minimal short axis length: The length in pixels of the minor direction of the fitted ellipse. Ellipses smaller than this threshold are removed.
- Maximal aspect ratio: Ratio of the length of major and minor axis. Ellipses with an aspect ratio larger than this value are removed.

Misc

- Smoothing factor: It sometimes occurs that the estimated standard deviation of the noise is lower than the true value. The smoothing factor is a multiplicative factor for the estimated standard deviation.
- Use inverted images: The ParticleSizer expects bright objects on a darker background. If images show the opposite, then this option should be checked.
- Show binary result: If selected the ParticleSizer shows the binary result.
- Ask me to select a region: If selected, the software allows you to select a specific region to analyse.

9 Appendix B: The ParticleSizer pipeline

Sections 9.1 and 9.2 give an overview of the processing pipeline implemented in the ParticleSizer. The methods “watershed for irregular structures”, “single particle mode” and “ellipse fitting” in the category segmentation are most important for this SOP and will be described more detailed in the sections 9.3, 9.4 and 9.5. For more details please refer to the deliverable 5.1.

9.1 Segmentation pipeline

The flow scheme of the segmentation pipeline is given in Figure 5. The standard deviation σ of the noise of recorded EM images is estimated using Immerkaer’s method (Immerkær 1996) and used to adapt an efficient, parallelized noise filter called “non local means”(Buades et al. 2005; Darbon et al. 2008) To identify particles on EM images, the background is removed using the rolling ball algorithm (parameterization depends on the image size) implemented in ImageJ. If the noise standard deviation is higher than the threshold T_1 a small median filter is applied to homogenize the particles. The result is the noise reduced and background subtracted (NRBS) image. The NRBS image is then binarized by a local adaptive threshold technique (Phansalkar et al. 2011) and saved as “Pre-Watershed image”. If single particle mode (SPM) is selected, all particles with a convexity smaller than T_2 are removed. When the SPM is deactivated the agglomerates are splitted into primary particles by a user selected technique which provides an initial identification of particles (segmentation). In post-processing steps possible artifacts introduced by the segmentation procedure are removed before geometrical features and size distributions are extracted. The post-processing steps are described in the next section.

Figure 5 Pre-processing pipeline

9.2 Post-Processing pipeline

The flow scheme of the post-processing pipeline is given in Figure 6. Starting from the segmented image resulting from the segmentation pipeline, all objects which are outside of user-defined limits of the geometrical features are removed. Default values are provided but the software also allows for an individual adaption of the limits to account for non-standard images. In a second step objects which have an object-to-background (OTB) intensity difference in the NRBS Images lower than T_3 (as configured in the settings manager) are considered as artefacts and are removed. When ellipse fitting is activated the ellipses are fitted to the particle boundaries to expose potential overlapping. However, the segmentation process often results in objects showing rough boundaries, which is corrected by applying a shape smoothing algorithm using Fourier descriptors when ellipse fitting is deactivated. Geometrical features extracted from the remaining objects are listed in a results table, and a particle size distribution based on the minimal Feret diameter (including also X_{50} values) is displayed in a graphical format. The complete results can also be exported for more detailed processing, if required.

Figure 6: Post-processing pipeline

9.3 Irregular watershed

The irregular watershed technique combines a conventional watershed splitting with a morphological erosion. The procedure starts with the binary image I . The image L with watershed lines is calculated the following way:

$$L = I \cap W(I)$$

where $W()$ is a conventional watershed splitting based on the euclidean distance map and \cap the logical AND operation.

In a next step connected components of image L are eroded. The erosion of a connected component is stopped when a convexity larger than a user defined threshold (0.7 is used by default) is reached or when the component is fully eroded. This results in image E which contains those connected components which fulfill the convexity condition. In the final step watershed lines in L which are crossing objects in E are rejected. This method successfully splits overlapping irregular objects but prevents oversegmentation.

9.4 Ellipse fitting

The combined approach couples a conventional watershed splitting based on the euclidean distance map with the direct ellipse fitting method. Figure 7 illustrates the principle of the method: The objects in the input image (Figure 7a) are splitted by the watershed technique (Figure 7b).

Figure 7: Ellipse fitting method (A) Input image of 5 overlapping circles, (B) splitted objects by conventional watershed technique, (C) the extracted watershed lines and (D) the ellipses fitted to the contours of the objects in image B rejecting all contour points which have a watershed line (image C) in the direct neighbourhood

By combining Figure 7a and Figure 7b by a logical XOR operation the watershed lines are extracted (Figure 7c). Contour lines of the objects in image B are then extracted and all contour points which have a watershed line in the direct neighbourhood are rejected. Finally an ellipse is fitted (Fitzgibbon et al. 1999) to the remaining contour data of the objects (Figure 7d).

Figure 8: Au nanoparticle agglomerate analysed by the ParticleSize software in (B) default mode and (C) ellipse fitting mode

Figure 8 shows a comparison of the conventional watershed method with the ellipse fitting approach using a Au nanoparticle agglomerate. The results demonstrate that the ellipse fitting provides a better estimate of the effective size of ellipsoidal overlapping particles compared to the conventional watershed approach.

9.5 Single particle mode

In cases, where agglomerates cannot be well dispersed, the proper segmentation of the agglomerates may not be possible. For such cases, “single particle mode” (SPM) is implemented in the ParticleSizer software. In the SPM, agglomerates are rejected and only primary particles - defined as particles with a high convexity - are included in the analyses. In the context of the ParticleSizer software the term “high convexity” is defined as follows:

A particle has a high convexity when the ratio of the perimeter of the convex hull and the perimeter of the outer contour is larger than 0.7.

10 References

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